

EFFECT OF ZINC APPLICATION ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF MUSTARD (BRASSICA JUNCEA L)

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ABSTRACT

The experiment conducted during 2022-23 to effect of zinc application on the growth and yield of mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.). The experiment was laid at the Students' Experimental Farm, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam in a three replicated Randomized complete block design. The treatments included $T_1 = 00 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ (control zinc), $T_2 = \text{Zn } 1 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $T_3 = \text{Zn } 3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $T_4 = \text{Zn } 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ and $T_5 = \text{Zn } 7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$. The results shows that the $\text{Zn } 7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ resulted maximum 69.57 m^{-2} plant population, 129.95 cm plant height, 18.00 branches plant^{-1} , 301.33 pods plant^{-1} , 12.00 seeds pod^{-1} , 4.66 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 2068 kg ha^{-1} seed yield. The mustard crop receiving $\text{Zn } 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ resulted 69.00 m^{-2} plant population, 127.33 cm plant height, 17.21 branches plant^{-1} , 297.03 pods plant^{-1} , 11.50 seeds pod^{-1} , 3.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 2015 kg ha^{-1} seed yield. $\text{Zn } 3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ also affected resulted 68.21 m^{-2} plant population, 125.00 cm plant height, 16.14 branches plant^{-1} , 287.67 pods plant^{-1} , 11.00 seeds pod^{-1} , 3.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1720 kg ha^{-1} seed yield. The mustard crop with $\text{Zn } 1 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ resulted 67.51 m^{-2} plant population, 120.31 cm plant height, 15.33 branches plant^{-1} , 280.00 pods plant^{-1} , 10.59 seeds pod^{-1} , 3.00 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1361 kg ha^{-1} seed yield. However, the 00 kg ha^{-1} (control zinc) resulted minimum 66.62 m^{-2} plant population, 118.52 cm plant height, 14.08 branches plant^{-1} , 270.00 pods plant^{-1} , 10.00 seeds pod^{-1} , 2.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1091 kg ha^{-1} seed yield. It was concluded that the effect of zinc levels on the growth and yield traits of mustard was remarkable ($P < 0.05$) and $\text{Zn } 7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ produced maximum seed yield (2068 kg ha^{-1}) than $\text{Zn } 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ (2015 kg ha^{-1}) and $\text{Zn } 3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ (1720 kg ha^{-1}).

Keywords: *Brassica juncea*, zinc nutrition, seed yield and quality

INTRODUCTION

Mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) is important Rabi oilseed crop which belongs to the family Cruciferae (Verma et al., 2020). Mustard is an energy rich crop which requires the major, secondary and micronutrients in adequate quantity for higher production. Mustard is quite responsive to micronutrients like zinc (Zn), which plays important role in growth and development of the crop (Yanthan et al., 2021). Oil seed-based cropping pattern especially mustard may lead to a higher profit and also contribute to preserve soil fertility. Mustard is a drought-tolerant crop that can be grown in residual soil moisture without the use of additional water (Chowhan et al., 2021). There are number of species producing edible oil mainly the species and sub-species in the Brassicaceae family (Shekhawat et al., 2017). The oil is one of the most preferred cooking oils and is a good quality preservative, especially for the preparation of pickles. It contributes about 16-20 % towards domestic edible oils production. Its tender leaves are consumed as vegetables and seeds are used as condiments (Ahmad et al., 2017). The production of oil along with good quality forage such as stems and leaves, owing to their low fibre and high protein concentration, increases the importance of mustard (Dhaliwal et al., 2021). The global production of mustard and its oil is around 38-42 and 12- 14 million tonnes respectively (Nayak et al., 2020). Plants with lower uptake of zinc appear to be stunted as well. Plant Zn efficiency involves Zn uptake, transport, and utilization; plants with high Zn efficiency display high yield and significant growth under low Zn supply and offer a promising and sustainable production crops (Hacisalihoglu, 2020). Zinc fertilizer application causes root and shoot growth during the growing season and therefore, lead to increased seed yield. Zinc also has the role in photosynthesis and nitrogen metabolism and it helps in regulating the auxin concentration in plant. It promotes flower setting and help in proper development of fruits. It also helps in carbohydrates transformation and sulphur metabolism. The grain and straw yield were also significantly increased by the application of zinc (Mishra et al., 2022). The requirement of vegetable oils and fats will be much higher in

coming years in view of ever-increasing population (Kumar et al., 2016). Zinc is an important constituent of several enzymes which regulates various metabolic processes in the plants and also influences the formation of several growth hormones like IAA in plants. Zinc stimulates the pod setting, seed formation and oil synthesis in the seeds of mustard and it increases the biological seed and stover yield of mustard (Raku et al., 2023). Zinc has vital role in carbohydrate and protein metabolism as well as it controls the plant growth hormone indole acetic acid (IAA). It is an essential component of dehydrogenase, proteinase and promotes starch formation, seed maturation and production (Geremew et al., 2023). Soil application of zinc is normally made at the seeding of crop, sometimes, Zn deficiency appears due to the low amount of Zn as recommended and low temperature as required during the crop growth. Deficiency of zinc can also appear after seeding of the crop in soils with high phosphorus contents. Zinc sulphate improves phosphorus utilization and regulates plant growth and increase leaf size, promotes silking, hastens maturity and increase to test weight (Sultana et al., 2020). Zinc (Zn) play an essential function in plant growth and development under optimal concentrations (Halim et al., 2023). Zinc, included in this category, has essential roles in binding of protein, regulation of enzyme activity, transcriptional and translational regulation, and signal transduction in being a component and co-factor of several enzymes. The deficiency of Zn results in necrotic spots, leaf chlorosis, nutrient imbalance, altered cell division, and reduced photosynthesis and growth (Ramya et al., 2022).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A research project was undertaken at the Department of Agronomy's Students' Farm at Sindh Agriculture University in Tando Jam to examine the effect of zinc application on the growth and yield of mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.). The experiment was structured using a completely randomized block design, with each plot measuring 3 m x 4 m (12 m²). Land preparation techniques tailored for sunflower cultivation were

employed, and the local mustard variety S-9 was selected for the study, with three replications. Zinc fertilizer was administered through recommended dosages.

Culture Practices

The soil underwent meticulous preparation, involving two rounds of ploughing and leveling before seed sowing. Each treatment received the requisite quantity of farmyard manure during the sowing process. Zinc was consistently administered at different stages of Mustard growth throughout the duration of the study. To monitor the agronomic attributes of the plants, five specimens were selected from each plot at five-day intervals during the initial 10 days following crop emergence.

T1 = 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc)

T2 = Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹

T3 = Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹

T4 = Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹

T5 = Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹

The Mustard crop received two timely irrigations, and measures were taken to control diseases, weeds, and pests at the experimental sites. Fifteen plants were taken from each experimental unit throughout the maturity stage in order to determine their plant population, plant height (cm), Branches plant⁻¹ and Pods plant⁻¹. The seed heads were separated from each plant, threshed, and used to calculate the number of Seeds pod⁻¹, Seed index (1000-seeds weight, g), Seed yield (kg ha⁻¹) all of which were recorded.

Statistical analysis

The gathered data underwent analysis utilizing ANOVA with the assistance of Statistix-8.1 Computer Software (Statistix, 2006). When necessary, the LSD test was employed to assess the efficacy of different treatments.

RESULTS

Plant population (m⁻²)

The impact of zinc on the plant population (m⁻²) of mustard variety S-9 was examined. The analysis of variance indicated a significant (P<0.05) influence of different zinc levels on the plant population (m⁻²) of mustard. The results showed that the maximum plant population at

maturity was observed (69.57 m⁻²) when the mustard was given 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn, followed by 5 kg ha⁻¹ (69.00 m⁻²) and 3 kg ha⁻¹ (68.21 m⁻²) of Zn. Conversely, the plant population at maturity of mustard was decreased to 67.51 m⁻² for 1 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn. However, the lowest plant population of mustard (66.62 m⁻²) was observed in the control group (0 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn). This suggests that applying 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn is highly beneficial for achieving maximum plant population (m⁻²) at maturity.

Plant height (cm)

The effect of zinc in mustard was investigated and the results in regarding to plant height (cm) of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance illustrated significant (P<0.05) effect of different levels of zinc on plant height (cm) of mustard. The results indicated that the plant height at maturity was maximum (129.95 cm) when the mustard was given Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹, followed by (127.33 cm and 125.00 cm) with Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹. The plant height at maturity of mustard was further decreased to 120.31 cm for Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. However, minimum (118.52 cm) plant height of mustard was observed with 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc). This indicates that the Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ is highly beneficial for obtaining maximum plant height (cm) at maturity.

Branches plant⁻¹

The effect of zinc on the branches plant⁻¹ of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance revealed a significant (P<0.05) impact of different zinc levels on the branches plant⁻¹ of mustard. The findings showed that the branches plant⁻¹ at maturity were highest (18.00) when the mustard was treated with 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn, followed by 5 kg ha⁻¹ (17.21) and 3 kg ha⁻¹ (16.14) of Zn. Conversely, the branches plant⁻¹ at maturity of mustard were decreased to 15.33 for 1 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn. However, the minimum branches plant⁻¹ of mustard (14.08) were observed in the control group (0 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn). These results suggest that applying 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn is highly beneficial for achieving maximum branches plant⁻¹ at maturity.

Pods plant⁻¹

The effect of zinc in mustard was investigated and the results in regarding to pods plant⁻¹ (cm) of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance illustrated significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of different levels of zinc on pods plant⁻¹ of mustard. The results indicated that the pods plant⁻¹ at maturity was maximum (301.33) when the mustard was given Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹, followed by (291.03 and

287.67) with Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹. The pods plant⁻¹ at maturity of mustard was further decreased to 280.00 for Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. However, minimum (270.00) pods plant⁻¹ of mustard was observed with 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc). This indicates that the Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ is highly beneficial for obtaining maximum pods plant⁻¹ at maturity.

Table 1. Different levels of Zinc applications on the growth parameters of mustard

Treatments	Plant population (m ⁻²)	Plant height (cm)	Branches plant ⁻¹	Pods plant ⁻¹
T1 = 00 kg ha ⁻¹ (control zinc)	66.62 e	118.52 e	14.08 e	270.00 d
T2 = Zn 1 kg ha ⁻¹	67.51 d	120.31 d	15.33 d	280.00 d
T3 = Zn 3 kg ha ⁻¹	68.21 c	125.00 c	16.14 c	287.67 c
T4 = Zn 5 kg ha ⁻¹	69.00 b	127.33 b	17.21 b	291.03 b
T5 = Zn 7 kg ha ⁻¹	69.57 a	129.95 a	18.00 a	301.33 a
S.E	0.278	1.361	0.055	1.528
P value	2.9236	2.2298	0.1307	4.8857
LSD (0.05)	1.2678	0.9669	0.0567	2.1187

Seeds pod⁻¹

The effect of zinc in mustard was investigated and the results in regarding to seeds pod⁻¹ (cm) of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance illustrated significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of different levels of zinc on seeds pod⁻¹ of mustard. The results indicated that the seeds pod⁻¹ at maturity was maximum (12.00) when the mustard was given Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹, followed by (11.50 and 11.00) with Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹. The seeds pod⁻¹ at maturity of mustard was further decreased to 10.59 for Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. However, minimum (10.00) seeds pod⁻¹ of mustard was observed with 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc). This indicates that the Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ is highly beneficial for obtaining maximum seeds pod⁻¹ at maturity.

index at maturity of mustard was decreased to 3.00 g for 1 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn. However, the minimum seed index of mustard (2.50 g) was observed in the control group (0 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn). These results suggest that applying 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn is highly beneficial for achieving maximum seed index at maturity.

Seed index (1000-seeds weight, g)

The effect of zinc on the seed index (cm) of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance revealed a significant ($P < 0.05$) impact of different zinc levels on the seed index of mustard. The findings showed that the seed index at maturity was highest (4.66 g) when the mustard was treated with 7 kg ha⁻¹ of Zn, followed by 5 kg ha⁻¹ (4.06 g) and 3 kg ha⁻¹ (3.50 g) of Zn. Conversely, the seed

Seed yield (kg ha⁻¹)

The effect of zinc in mustard was investigated and the results in regarding to seed yield (cm) of mustard variety S-9. The analysis of variance illustrated significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of different levels of zinc on seed yield of mustard. The results indicated that the seed yield at maturity was maximum (2068 kg ha⁻¹) when the mustard was given Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹, followed by (2015 kg ha⁻¹ and 1720 kg ha⁻¹) with Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹. The seed yield at maturity of mustard was further decreased to 1360 kg ha⁻¹ for Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. However, minimum (1091 kg ha⁻¹) seed yield of mustard was observed with 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc). This indicates that the Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ is highly beneficial for obtaining maximum seed yield at maturity.

Table 2. Different levels of Zinc applications on the growth parameters of mustard

Treatments	Seeds pod ⁻¹	Seed index (1000-seeds weight, g)	Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
T1 = 00 kg ha ⁻¹ (control zinc)	10.00 e	2.50 e	1091
T2 = Zn 1 kg ha ⁻¹	10.59 d	3.00 d	1361 e
T3 = Zn 3 kg ha ⁻¹	11.00 c	3.50 c	1720 d
T4 = Zn 5 kg ha ⁻¹	11.50 b	4.06 b	2015 c
T5 = Zn 7 kg ha ⁻¹	12.00 a	4.66 a	2068 b
S.E	0.040	0.030	5.132 a
P value	0.0760	0.0619	9.1015
LSD (0.05)	0.0329	0.0268	3.9469

DISCUSSION

Mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) is important Rabi oilseed crop which belongs to the family Cruciferae (Jha et al., 2023). Mustard is an energy rich crop which requires the major, secondary and micronutrients in adequate quantity for higher production. Mustard is quite responsive to micronutrients like zinc (Zn), which plays important role in growth and development of the crop (Salmasi et al., 2024). The present study shows that the Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ resulted maximum 69.57 m² plant population, 129.95 cm plant height, 18.00 branches plant⁻¹, 301.33 pods plant⁻¹, 12.00 seeds pod⁻¹, 4.66 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 2068 kg ha⁻¹ seed yield. The mustard crop receiving Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ resulted 69.00 m² plant population, 127.33 cm plant height, 17.21 branches plant⁻¹, 297.03 pods plant⁻¹, 11.50 seeds pod⁻¹, 3.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 2015 kg ha⁻¹ seed yield. Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹ also affected resulted 68.21 m² plant population, 125.00 cm plant height, 16.14 branches plant⁻¹, 287.67 pods plant⁻¹, 11.00 seeds pod⁻¹, 3.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1720 kg ha⁻¹ seed yield. The mustard crop with Zn 1 kg ha⁻¹ resulted 67.51 m² plant population, 120.31 cm plant height, 15.33 branches plant⁻¹, 280.00 pods plant⁻¹, 10.59 seeds pod⁻¹, 3.00 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1361 kg ha⁻¹ seed yield. However, the 00 kg ha⁻¹ (control zinc) resulted minimum 66.62 m² plant population, 118.52 cm plant height, 14.08 branches plant⁻¹, 270.00 pods plant⁻¹, 10.00 seeds pod⁻¹, 2.50 g seed index (1000-seeds weight) and 1091 kg ha⁻¹ seed yield. It was concluded that the

effect of zinc levels on the growth and yield traits of mustard was remarkable (P<0.05) and Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ produced maximum seed yield (2068 kg ha⁻¹) than Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ (2015 kg ha⁻¹) and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹ (1720 kg ha⁻¹). The findings of the present research are further confirmed by many past researchers of Latha et al. (2018) who reported application of zinc significantly improved the crop growth and seed yield in mustard. Mirzapour et al. (2017) reported that higher rates of zinc improved the seed yield. Beulah et al. (2022) found that the effect of zinc application on the growth and (head diameter, 100-seed weight, number of seeds, and harvest index) seed yield factors of mustard variety KBSH-44 (1997 kg ha⁻¹ yield). Neena et al. (2016) observed that the uptake of K in maize and mustard and the availability of K in the soil were significantly increased by zinc nutrition, highlighting the positive interaction between Zn and K. Application of 25 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹ registered the highest K uptake in both crops, and the highest mustard harvest. Mehera, (2022) argued that it may also be possible to improve crop yields on Zn-deficient soils by exploiting genotypic differences in Zn uptake and tissue-use efficiency that exist within crop species. Zhang et al. (2023) evaluated that effect of Zinc (Zn at 3.15, 4.20 and 5.25 kg ha⁻¹) and Boron (B at 2.1, 4.2 and 6.3 kg ha⁻¹) application on biochemical and quality parameters and yield in mustard was studied in Maharashtra, India. The study revealed that combined application of Zn (5.25 kg ha⁻¹) and B (6.3 kg ha⁻¹) was most effective followed by Zn

(5.25 kg ha⁻¹) or B (2.1 kg ha⁻¹). The combination showed increase over the control in chlorophyll content, nitrogen content in dry matter and seed, phosphorus content in dry matter and seed, potassium content in dry matter and seed, and oil and protein content in seed. Similarly, the combined application of Zn and B exhibited increase over control in straw yield, harvest index, translocation efficiency, 100-seed weight and seed yield plant⁻¹ (Vidmahe et al., 2022). The combined application of Zn and B exhibited increase over control in straw yield, harvest index, translocation efficiency, 100-seed weight and seed yield plant⁻¹ (Gautam et al., 2020). Patil et al. (2016) applied zinc (15, 20 and 25 kg ha⁻¹) and boron (20, 40 and 60 kg ha⁻¹) and reported that combined application of 25 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹ and 60 kg borax ha⁻¹ significantly increased the seed yield of the crop over the control. This increase in yield may be attributed to the increase in yield contributing characters such as yield, total number of seeds and 100-seed weight (Manjushri et al., 2018). Several studies have shown that zinc deficiency can significantly reduce the growth and yield of mustard crops. For example, a study conducted by Ram et al. (2019) found that the application of zinc significantly increased the plant height, leaf area, and dry matter yield of mustard plants. Similarly, a study by Tyagi et al. (2022) reported that the application of zinc increased the seed yield and oil content of mustard. Zinc also plays a crucial role in the uptake and transportation of other nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. A study by Rauf et al. (2017) showed that the application of zinc increased the nitrogen and phosphorus uptake in mustard plants, which subsequently led to an increase in the crop yield. The authors suggested that zinc application can improve the nutrient use efficiency of mustard crops. Moreover, zinc application has also been found to improve the quality of mustard oil. A study by Du et al. (2020) reported that the application of zinc significantly increased the oil content and reduced the levels of free fatty acids in mustard oil. The authors suggested that zinc application can improve the nutritional value and shelf life of mustard oil. However, excessive zinc application can also have negative effects on mustard growth

and yield. A study by Chaudhry et al. (2020) reported that the application of high levels of zinc reduced the plant height, leaf area, and biomass of mustard plants. The authors suggested that excessive zinc application can lead to toxicity and inhibit the growth of mustard crops. In conclusion, zinc is an essential micronutrient that plays a vital role in the growth and development of mustard crops. Zinc deficiency can significantly reduce the growth and yield of mustard crops, while adequate zinc application can improve the crop yield and quality of mustard oil. However, excessive zinc application can have negative effects on mustard growth and yield. Thus, it is crucial to apply zinc in an optimal amount for the best results.

CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that the effect of zinc levels on the growth and yield traits of mustard was remarkable ($P < 0.05$) and Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ produced maximum seed yield (2068 kg ha⁻¹) than Zn 5 kg ha⁻¹ (2015 kg ha⁻¹) and Zn 3 kg ha⁻¹ (1720 kg ha⁻¹).

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the present study it was recommended that mustard variety S-9 recommended for general cultivation due to its better yield performance. T₅ = Zn 7 kg ha⁻¹ recommended on the basis of higher seed yield.

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